
Humane and Effective Return Governance: Evidence, Gaps and Pathways for the European Union and its Member States

Terry Martin
Science-Policy Interface Agency

Executive Summary

- EU return governance is facing an enduring implementation gap: orders to leave remain high, while effective returns and sustainable reintegration outcomes remain limited. GAPS evidence indicates that addressing this gap cannot be achieved through “more enforcement” alone; it requires rights-based procedures, credible reintegration pathways, transparent data, and cooperation models that are partnership-based rather than purely transactional.
 - Across Member States, a narrative of “voluntariness” often masks a continuum of coercion. Indirect pressure (-threats of detention, withdrawal of services and basic rights, and informal “persuasion” practices) undermines genuine consent, erodes trust, and increases the likelihood of re-migration.
 - Post-return outcomes across Afghanistan, Iraq, Nigeria and Tunisia show persistent hardship, insecurity and weak access to livelihoods and services. Where assistance exists, it is frequently short-term, bureaucratic, unevenly accessible, and disconnected from structural conditions.
- Many returnees express onward or re-migration aspirations when reintegration is not viable or sustainable.
- Return diplomacy and readmission cooperation work better when embedded in comprehensive packages that include reintegration support, legal mobility opportunities and mutual trust. Return-focused diplomacy can generate hidden costs and human-rights trade-offs, particularly when procedural safeguards are weakened for “efficiency”. However, assurances on human rights compliance and procedural safeguards are essential for a successful and sustainable implementation of return agreements/arrangements.
 - Accountability deficits remain acute: return statistics and financial data are fragmented, methodologically inconsistent and often opaque. Cost-benefit assessment is therefore weak, despite the high direct and indirect costs of coerced return.
 - Because non-return is the empirical reality in many cases, alternatives to return (ATR) are not marginal. They are structurally

central to governance and require clear minimum standards, judicial oversight and predictable pathways out of prolonged limbo.

- This brief provides evidence-based pathways and recommendations for the European Commission, the European Parliament, and EU Member States to advance return governance that is both humane and effective - consistent with fundamental rights and the EU's constitutional principles and norms.

What GAPS did and what evidence underpins this brief

GAPs combined multi-country policy and institutional analysis with field-based evidence on returnees' lived experiences and the practices of actors across return infrastructures.

This brief draws especially on the GAPs project's: (i) comparative findings on return infrastructures, South–South returns, public attitudes, and reintegration; (ii) comparative survey of returnees in Afghanistan, Iraq, Nigeria and Tunisia; and (iii) work on promising practices, migrant aspirations, alternatives to return, human-rights trade-offs and costs; (iv) study of migrant aspirations; and (v) investigation of return cooperation.

Evidence and Analysis: what needs to change

1) A continuum of coercion within return infrastructures

Return is implemented through complex 'Return Migration Infrastructures' (RMIs): webs of state agencies, EU bodies, international organisations, NGOs, local authorities, private actors, and informal practices. GAPs findings show that, in practice, assisted/voluntary and forced return are often interwoven along a continuum of coercion rather than being distinct categories.

- Informal and opaque practices are entrenched across RMIs, ranging from 'persuasion' tactics to unlawful detention, pushbacks and pushforwards.
- The use (or threat) of detention and the withdrawal of essential services function as indirect pressure, undermining genuine voluntariness.
- Returns frequently overlap with spaces of reception, asylum processing and protection, creating 'grey zones' where safeguards are weakened and coercion is normalised.

Policy takeaway: credibility, legitimacy and effectiveness require procedural safeguards, independent monitoring, and the separation of asylum/protection infrastructures from return enforcement.

2) Reintegration is the missing link - and a determinant of effectiveness

GAPs post-return evidence indicates that reintegration support is often inadequate, short-term and poorly aligned with structural conditions in countries of return. This undermines sustainability and increases incentives for re-migration.

Comparative survey patterns (Afghanistan, Iraq, Nigeria, Tunisia) include:

- High rates of forced return in several contexts (notably Afghanistan and Nigeria), and limited perceived choice in 'voluntary' return decisions in others.
- Substantial reliance on private resources (savings, family networks) to establish livelihoods in Afghanistan and Iraq; institutionalised support is more visible in Nigeria but does not guarantee long-term reintegration.
- Persistent hardship after return - linked to insecurity, unemployment, limited services, stigma and psychosocial distress - alongside sustained aspirations for onward mobility when prospects are poor.

Implication: EU and Member State approaches need long-term reintegration

strategies that integrate psychosocial care, livelihoods, documentation support and community-level inclusion, delivered through local partnerships and monitored beyond the immediate post-return phase.

3) International cooperation works best when partnership-based and comprehensive

GAPs comparative findings on return diplomacy show two broad pathways in bilateral readmission cooperation: (i) conditional cooperation through incentives, and (ii) cooperation based on historical affinity and relational continuity. The latter - together with comprehensive packages - tends to yield more sustainable outcomes than 'readmission-only' arrangements.

- Return arrangements often function as political exchanges (e.g., visas, development aid, diplomatic recognition) that can conceal asymmetric costs borne by migrants. Overcoming mistrust – within both the EU and returning countries – is essential.
- Although origin countries generally prefer bilateral cooperation, their approaches differ. Comprehensive packages offered by returning states, which favorably link migration, development, and reintegration, are perceived more positively than strictly formal or readmission-specific models or EU level readmission arrangement.
- Reintegration commitments and legal pathways in agreements are frequently weakly monitored, fragmented across institutions, and disconnected from measurable outcomes for returnees.
- Legal migration pathways promised by returning countries, such as EU Member States, are often limited, poorly funded, or constrained by restrictive eligibility criteria. This diminishes their value and raises doubts about the sincerity of cooperation.
- When returnees face harsh conditions and human rights violations before and during returns, the legitimacy and fairness of the

readmission process are further undermined.

Implication: the EU should rebalance cooperation away from extreme externalised enforcement solutions and towards predictable partnership frameworks linking reintegration, protection, and legal mobility opportunities.

4) Data opacity and cost blindness undermine accountability and policy learning

Across Member States, return data is often inconsistent, incomplete and methodologically weak, limiting evaluation. Financial information on the cost of return operations is particularly opaque, constraining parliamentary scrutiny and public accountability. Data opacity may also be a political decision, not merely bureaucratic, to shield from policies that may be scrutinised for being high-cost.

- In Germany, a stock-taking exercise shows that a comprehensive cost-benefit analysis is not feasible with available data: costs are fragmented across federal and Länder budgets, reporting periods, and institutional silos.
- Forced removals can become disproportionately expensive, driven by detention, escorts, and charter operations; indirect costs include the loss of investment in integration and negative labour-market and social effects.
- Data protection concerns, while legitimate, are sometimes used to block coherent data collection and transparency mechanisms.

Implication: evidence-based return governance requires harmonised reporting, cost transparency, and rights-compatible data governance that enables oversight without undermining personal data protection.

5) Alternatives to return are structurally central and require minimum standards

Because non-return remains widespread in EU Member States, alternatives to return (ATR) - regularisation, toleration statuses, employment-linked residence, and other non-removal arrangements - are a de facto core element of return governance. GAPs analysis shows ATR instruments can reduce harm and increase predictability, but they also entail human-rights trade-offs when they institutionalise prolonged temporariness, discretionary control, or unequal access to rights.

- Promising practices create time-bound pathways out of precarious status and reduce 'limbo', while ensuring proportionality and judicial oversight.
- Early, accurate information and counselling - delivered by trusted intermediaries - supports informed decision-making and migrant agency.
- Non-custodial approaches and individualised case management reduce reliance on detention and can improve compliance without coercion.
- Monitoring and independent oversight mechanisms help deter abuse, enable learning, and protect fundamental rights.

Implication: new EU return legislation should include ATR guidelines defining minimum standards, oversight, and legal certainty for

non-returnable persons, alongside expanded safe and legal pathways.

6) Public attitudes: legitimacy depends on fairness, transparency and trust

GAPs public-attitudes research indicates that support for return is conditional and varies by national context. Attitudes are strongly shaped by perceptions of fairness, integration, economic contribution, and trust in institutions; political polarisation is a key driver.

- Among the 5,000 participants surveyed in five countries (Germany, Sweden, Poland, The Netherlands, and Greece), many respondents support return primarily for those perceived as 'non-compliant' (e.g., criminality, welfare dependence), while resisting return of well-integrated or working people.
- Dissatisfaction with government performance on asylum and return is widespread, reinforcing demands for credibility while also heightening risk of rights-erosion if policy communication is weak.
- Meaningful interaction between citizens and migrants correlates with lower support for restrictive return approaches.

Implication: communication strategies should be transparent and evidence-led, while policy design must demonstrate procedural fairness and rights compliance to sustain legitimacy.

Policy Recommendations

Recommendations are grouped for EU-level action (Commission/Parliament), and for Member States' implementation. They are intended to be mutually reinforcing: enforcement capacity without safeguards and reintegration does not deliver sustainable outcomes.

A. Embed 'true voluntariness' and fundamental rights in all return procedures

1. Institutionally and procedurally separate assisted/voluntary return from forced removal pathways to avoid blurred lines between consent and coercion.
2. Guarantee access to independent legal aid, interpretation, an asylum procedure and psychosocial support early and throughout the return process; ensure adequate time to make decisions.
3. End indirect coercion practices, including the withdrawal of essential services and detention threats as 'persuasion' tools; enforce prohibitions and accountability for pushbacks/pushforwards.
4. Establish and resource independent monitoring mechanisms covering all stages of return, including pre-removal detention, removal operations, and post-return follow-up where feasible.

B. Make reintegration a core, long-term pillar of EU return governance

5. Develop comprehensive reintegration strategies that extend beyond short project cycles and are tailored to local contexts, integrating: documentation, housing, livelihoods, health care (including mental health), education and community inclusion.
6. Shift from sanction-based approaches toward supportive, individualised reintegration planning, using case management and needs assessments that incorporate vulnerability and child-best-interest considerations.

7. Invest in 'whole-of-the-route' planning: align pre-departure counselling, skills recognition and preparation with post-return support delivered through local actors; provide outcome monitoring at defined intervals after return.
8. Ensure that reintegration support is accessible beyond narrow eligibility categories and does not function as a substitute for rights protections during asylum and return procedures.

C. Rebalance international cooperation towards genuine partnerships

9. Prioritise comprehensive cooperation packages over 'readmission-only' deals, linking return with reintegration support, development measures and, where appropriate, legal mobility pathways.
10. Increase transparency and democratic oversight of return agreements, including parliamentary scrutiny and structured consultation with civil society in countries of destination and return.
11. Avoid externalised 'return hub' approaches that concentrate risks and weaken safeguards and accountability; where cooperation is pursued with third countries, make adherence to non-refoulement and due process non-negotiable.

D. Fix the data, accountability and cost architecture

12. Harmonise return data definitions and reporting across the EU (decisions, outcomes, safeguards, vulnerability screening, reintegration follow-up), with clear quality standards and independent auditability.
13. Harmonise return data definitions and reporting across the EU (decisions, outcomes, safeguards, vulnerability screening, reintegration follow-up), with clear quality standards and independent auditability.
14. Publish transparent financial reporting on return operations and external

programmes, enabling full cost–benefit analysis (including direct and indirect costs) while ensuring data protection compliance.

15. Create mechanisms for migrants to access their own data and contest inaccuracies; strengthen oversight of biometric and identity-verification processes.

E. Establish minimum standards for Alternatives to Return (ATR) and reduce long-term limbo

16. Incorporate EU-level ATR guidance into return governance: define minimum standards, time limits, and judicial oversight for non-returnable persons to increase predictability and reduce prolonged precariousness.
17. Support Member States in expanding feasible pathways for regular stay (e.g., employment-based residence, time-bound regularisation, toleration pathways) with

rights-compatible conditions and non-discriminatory access.

18. Scale promising practices: early information and counselling through trusted intermediaries; non-custodial case management; and independent oversight mechanisms.

Concluding note

The GAPs evidence suggests that the EU’s core challenge is not simply to increase the number of returns, but to reduce the structural drivers of non-sustainable return and non-return: rights deficits, weak reintegration, opaque data, and cooperation models that prioritise short-term political gains over long-term outcomes. A human, protective and effective return system is one that is procedurally fair, transparent, partnership-based, and capable of supporting durable post-return futures.

Cite as

Martin, T. (2026). “Humane and Effective Return Governance: Evidence, Gaps and Pathways for the European Union and its Member States” *GAPs 2nd EC Policy Brief*. DOI: 10.5281/zenodo.18419591

Project identity

Project name	GAPs: De-centring the Study of Migrant Returns and Readmission Policies in Europe and Beyond
Funding	EC Horizon Europe (Grant Agreement nr. 101094341)
Duration	2023-2026
Coordinators	Zeynep Sahin-Mencütek Bonn International Centre for Conflict Studies zeynep.mencutek@bicc.de Soner Barthoma Uppsala University soner.barthoma@crs.uu.se
Consortium	Uppsala University (Sweden) Bonn International Centre for Conflict Studies (Germany) Stichting Radboud Universiteit (Netherlands) Ozyegin Universitesi (Turkey) Hammurabi Human Rights Organization (Iraq) Svenska Forskningsinstitutet i Istanbul (Sweden/Turkey) Hashemite University (Jordan) Ethniko Kentro Koinonikon Erevnon (Greece) Association Migration Internationale (Morocco) Toronto Metropolitan University (Canada) University of Nigeria (Nigeria) Bilim Organization for Research and Social Studies (Afghanistan) Uniwersytet Warszawski (Poland) Migration Matters EV (Germany) University of Sousse (Tunisia) SPIA UG (Germany) University of Glasgow (UK)
Further reading	For more detailed analysis, please consult the GAPs project’s website – “Publications”: https://www.returnmigration.eu/publications-gaps See Annex for “Debunking Return Migration Policy Myths with the GAPs research”.

Project summary

GAPs is a Horizon Europe research project that aims to conduct a comprehensive multidisciplinary study of the drivers of return policies and the barriers to and enablers of international cooperation on return migration. The overall aim of the project is to examine the disconnects and discrepancies between expectations of return policies and their actual outcomes by decentering the dominant, one-sided understanding of “return policymaking.” To this end, GAPs:

- examines the shortcomings of the EU’s return governance;
- analyses enablers of and barriers to international cooperation, and
- explores the perspectives of migrants themselves to understand their knowledge, aspirations and experiences with return policies.

GAPs combines its approach with three innovative concepts:

- A focus on return migration infrastructures, which allows the project to analyse governance gaps;
- An analysis of return migration diplomacy to understand how relations between EU member states and third countries hinder cooperation on return and
- A trajectory approach which uses a socio-spatial and temporal lens to understand migrant agency.

GAPs is a three-year interdisciplinary research project (2023–2026) coordinated by Uppsala University and the Bonn International Centre for Conflict Studies (BICC) with 17 partners in 14 countries on four continents. GAPs’ fieldwork and desk research are conducted in several countries, including Afghanistan, Canada, Germany, Greece, Iraq, Jordan, the Netherlands, Nigeria, Morocco, Poland, Sweden, Tunisia, Türkiye, and the UK.

This project has received funding from the European Union’s Horizon Europe research and innovation programme under grant agreement 101094341.

ANNEX

Debunking Return Migration Policy Myths with the GAPS research

Zeynep Sahin-Mencütek (biic) & Soner Barthoma (Uppsala University)

	Policy Myth	Counter Evidence from GAPS Research	Link to Relevant GAPS output
1	Return is the end of a person's migration journey.	Return is just one moment in an ongoing journey, not an endpoint; returnees frequently want to remigrate and engage in circular mobility depending on opportunities.	WP1 framework paper https://www.returnmigration.eu/wp-series/framework-paper-on-the-concepts-and-typologies-on-returns-combined-with-four-conceptual-notes WP7 comparative report https://www.returnmigration.eu/wp-series/return-in-mobile-trajectories-wp7
2	Forced and voluntary returns are completely different types of returns. Assisted voluntary return options are genuinely chosen by migrants.	The boundary between forced and voluntary return is often blurred, as both usually involve coercion. Assisted voluntary return is frequently a choice made under duress rather than a genuine preference. Migrants resort to assisted return because viable alternatives are systematically foreclosed because of prolonged legal insecurity, restricted access to work and services, the risk of detention, or the threat of forced removal.	Iraq human rights tradeoffs https://www.returnmigration.eu/wp-series/political-and-human-rights-trade-offs-assisted-return-frameworks Article on coerced returns https://www.tandfonline.com/doi/full/10.1080/1369183X.2024.2371209
3	When armed conflict in the origin country ends, all displaced people from there are required to return and tend to go home.	Return decisions are shaped by a complex interplay of structural factors (conflict cessation, host-country conditions) and individuals' aspirations and capabilities. Displaced people may prioritise safety, dignity, and opportunity differently across locations, resulting in diverse outcomes, including delayed return, onward migration, circular mobility, or permanent settlement.	Dossier on return to Syria https://www.returnmigration.eu/wp-series/research-dossier-on-syrian-refugee-return-dynamics . WP8 comparative report (<i>forthcoming</i>)
4	Restrictive border controls and stringent asylum policies encourage migrants to return.	People continue to migrate despite increasing restrictions. Such barriers fail to deter movement and instead displace people towards longer, more clandestine and deadlier routes.	WP4 synthesis report https://www.returnmigration.eu/wp-series/return-migration-governance-in-the-african-and-middle-eastern-regions WP7 comparative report https://www.returnmigration.eu/wp-series/return-in-mobile-trajectories-wp7

5	<p>Detention is used as a last resort in removing rejected asylum seekers.</p>	<p>In practice, detention is widely deployed as a frontline tool in return procedures. Far from being exceptional, it is increasingly normalised. Detention is routinely used as a direct or indirect deterrence mechanism to discourage asylum claims and onward movement.</p>	<p>Greece report https://www.returnmigration.eu/wp-series/irregularisation-in-greece-spatial-carceral-temporal-aspects</p> <p>WP2 comparative report https://www.returnmigration.eu/wp-series/legal-and-policy-infrastructures-of-returns-in-eu-comparative-report-wp2</p> <p>WP8 comparative report</p>
6	<p>All administrative return decisions to return (or `removal orders`) respect migrants' rights.</p>	<p>Due to informality in administrative procedures, returns often involve human rights violations. Migrants are usually not sufficiently informed about their rights, available remedies, or the legal basis of return decisions. Removal orders and procedures do not always follow due process. And independent monitoring of return procedures is often not guaranteed.</p>	<p>WP3 comparative report https://www.returnmigration.eu/wp-series/return-migration-infrastructures-wp3-synthesis-report</p> <p>Iraq human rights tradeoffs https://www.returnmigration.eu/wp-series/political-and-human-rights-trade-offs-assisted-return-frameworks</p> <p>Nigeria EU cooperation https://www.returnmigration.eu/wp-series/research-digest-key-insights-on-nigeria-eu-migration-cooperation</p>
7	<p>The EU level return rate is relatively low, ranging from 20 per cent to 30 per cent.</p>	<p>EU-level return rates are not clear. This is the result of data fragmentation and accuracy issues that obscure national-level realities. This opacity is deepened by policies that prioritise return rates over post-return sustainability and reintegration, potentially undermining effectiveness and triggering remigration cycles.</p>	<p>Report on data https://www.returnmigration.eu/wp-series/gaps-data-repository-on-return-guideline-data-samples-and-codebook</p> <p>Germany report https://www.returnmigration.eu/wp-series/return-migration-infrastructures-in-germany</p>
8	<p>Origin or transit countries are passive recipients of return agreements.</p>	<p>Origin and transit countries are active and strategic partners in migration diplomacy, extracting political or financial concessions and shaping the terms and implementation of return agreements. Their bargaining power is enabled by the EU's strong prioritisation of return. Return diplomacy thus reflects asymmetric and dynamic power relations rather than unilateral EU control. This leverage has also enabled transit countries to position themselves as gatekeepers and increasingly engage with the push for returns to origin countries.</p>	<p>WP4 Synthesis Report https://www.returnmigration.eu/wp-series/return-migration-governance-in-the-african-and-middle-eastern-regions</p> <p>Report on Turkey https://www.returnmigration.eu/wp-series/eu-return-policies-the-case-of-turkey</p> <p>Report on Nigeria https://www.returnmigration.eu/wp-series/challenges-and-opportunities-for-nigerian-migrants-from-north-africa-in-the-context-of-eu-policies</p> <p>Report on Libya https://www.returnmigration.eu/wp-series/country-dossier-libya-return-migration-governance-african-middle-eastern-regions-role-of-eu</p>

9	<p>Migrants’ return home is usually smooth, and returnees can restart their lives thanks to support from their home countries or the IOM.</p>	<p>Returnees often find it difficult to return to the “home” they left behind. The support available to them is typically minimal and short-term, while they face demanding legal, economic, social and psychological conditions of reintegration.</p>	<p>Report on Georgia https://www.returnmigration.eu/wp-series/return-migration-infrastructures-in-poland-and-georgia</p> <p>WP8 Report on Afghanistan https://www.returnmigration.eu/wp-series/practices-and-experiences-of-returnees-in-afghanistan</p> <p>WP8 Report on Tunisia https://www.returnmigration.eu/wp-series/postreturn-practices-experiences-of-returnees-tunisia</p>
10	<p>Returns represent a threefold benefit for destination countries, origin countries, and migrants alike.</p>	<p>Returns carry both financial and social costs for destination countries. Meanwhile, origin countries often lack the capacity to absorb returnees because of their own structural issues. Many returnees have been forced to return and do not have sufficient resources to sustain themselves or to help develop their home countries.</p>	<p>Cost of returns https://www.returnmigration.eu/wp-series/cost-of-coerced-returns-in-germany</p> <p>WP8 comparative report</p>